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GDP in OECD Countries

The GDP in OECD countries grew by an average of 2354.9% between 1970 and 2023. The OECD calculates GDP values at purchasing power parity. Data is available from 1970 to 2023 for nearly all OECD countries.

GDP in OECD Countries in 2023. In 2023, the GDP of OECD countries showed significant disparities among nations, with the United States at the top with a GDP of \$27,348.00 billion. This figure underscores the enormous economic weight of the United States, which represents a substantial part of the global economy. Japan and Germany follow with \$6,249.93 billion and \$5,797.39 billion, respectively. These countries are known for their advanced economies, with Japan being a leader in technology and manufacturing, and Germany dominating European industry with its strong industrial and manufacturing base. France and the United Kingdom, with GDPs of \$4,134.31 billion and \$3,990.98 billion, respectively, are right behind. France maintains a solid, diversified economy with a strong presence in the energy and luxury goods sectors, while the United Kingdom, despite post-Brexit turmoil, continues to be a global financial center. Türkiye, with a GDP of \$3,631.57 billion, shows a rapidly growing economy despite political and economic challenges. Italy, with a GDP of \$3,424.22 billion, remains one of the major European economies, supported by its strong manufacturing tradition and tourism sector. Mexico, with a GDP of \$3,281.84 billion, is the largest economy in Latin America within the OECD, benefiting from a strong manufacturing and agricultural industry. South Korea, with a GDP of \$2,808.86 billion, is another technological giant, known for its innovation in the electronics and automotive sectors. Spain and Canada, with GDPs of \$2,544.20 billion and \$2,542.62 billion, respectively, show strong and diversified economies, with Spain benefiting from a robust tourism sector and Canada from vast natural resources. Australia, with a GDP of \$1,974.27 billion, stands out for its economy based on natural resources and services, while Poland, with \$1,797.18 billion, emerges as one of the fastest-growing economies in Central Europe. The Netherlands, with a GDP of \$1,390.38 billion, boasts a strong economy based on international trade and logistics. Colombia, with a GDP of \$1,138.99 billion, represents a major emerging economy in South America. Switzerland and Belgium, with GDPs of \$831.81 billion and \$826.41 billion, respectively, show stable and developed economies, with Switzerland being a global financial center and Belgium a hub for the European Union. Sweden and Norway, with GDPs of \$733.04 billion and \$700.82 billion, are known for their advanced economies and strong welfare state sectors. Austria, with a GDP of \$668.88 billion, and Ireland, with \$667.74 billion, maintain solid and competitive economies, with Ireland benefiting from a favorable tax environment for multinationals. Chile and the Czech Republic, with GDPs of \$645.34 billion and \$579.6 billion, respectively, represent emerging and dynamic economies in Latin America and Central Europe. Israel, with a GDP of \$529.12 billion, is recognized for its strong technology and innovation industry. Portugal and

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Denmark, with GDPs of \$507.84 billion and \$452.05 billion, are developed economies with a mix of industrial and service sectors. Hungary and Greece, with GDPs of \$436.26 billion and \$422.52 billion, show growing economies with significant tourism and manufacturing sectors. Finland, with a GDP of \$360.08 billion, is known for its advanced educational system and strong technology industry. New Zealand, with a GDP of \$278.45 billion, maintains an economy based on agriculture and tourism. Slovakia and Costa Rica, with GDPs of \$240.26 billion and \$148.13 billion, respectively, represent emerging economies with growing industrial and service sectors. Lithuania, with a GDP of \$148.1 billion, is one of the rapidly developing Baltic economies. Slovenia and Luxembourg, with GDPs of \$115.46 billion and \$95.37 billion, respectively, show solid economies with a mix of industry and financial services. Finally, Latvia and Estonia, with GDPs of \$79.39 billion and \$66.34 billion, respectively, represent growing Baltic economies with strong technology sectors. Iceland, with a GDP of \$30.12 billion, is the smallest economy among OECD countries but has a high standard of living and an economy based on tourism and fishing. In summary, the GDP of OECD countries in 2023 highlights marked economic disparities, with the United States dominating the global landscape. European, Asian, and Latin American economies show different levels of development and specialization, contributing to a diverse economic landscape within the OECD.

GDP Trends in OECD Countries Between 1970 and 2023. The analysis of GDP trends in OECD member countries from 1970 to 2023 reveals significant and varied increases among the different nations, reflecting both global economic changes and specific internal dynamics of each country. In general, all OECD countries have experienced significant GDP growth, although with notable variations in absolute and percentage terms. For example, Australia's GDP increased from \$58.91 billion in 1970 to \$1,974.27 billion in 2023, with an absolute change of \$1,915.36 billion and a percentage growth of 3251.3%. This increase is attributable to economic stability, abundant natural resources, and an economic policy favorable to foreign investment. Austria also showed a remarkable increase, with an absolute change of \$640.31 billion and a 2241.2% increase, benefiting from a strong industrial base, a solid banking system, and integration into the European Union, which facilitated trade and investment. Belgium recorded an increase of \$789.13 billion, marking a percentage increase of 2116.8%. Belgium's strategic position, connected to major European trade routes, supported this growth. Canada, with a change of \$2,443.36 billion and a percentage growth of 2461.6%, benefited from abundant natural resources, a strong manufacturing sector, and privileged access to the U.S. market. Denmark saw a GDP increase of \$431.09 billion (2056.7%) thanks to a diversified economy and a strong renewable energy sector. Finland recorded GDP growth of \$344.51 billion, with a 2212.7% increase, supported by an excellent educational system and advanced technological innovation. France saw its GDP increase by \$3,942.58 billion, with a percentage change of 2056.3%, supported by a diversified industry and a strong services sector. Germany, with an increase of \$5,483.26 billion (1745.5%), benefited from a solid industrial base and its position as the leading European economy. Greece, despite recent economic crises, saw a GDP increase of \$395.01 billion, with a percentage growth of 1435.9%. Iceland recorded the highest increase among OECD countries, with a 3712.7% growth, although the absolute value is relatively low, with an increase of \$29.33 billion. Ireland showed an impressive growth of 9110.2%, with a GDP increase of \$660.49 billion, reflecting the country's attractiveness to multinationals and a favorable tax environment. Italy saw a GDP increase of \$3,228.86 billion, with a percentage growth of 1652.8%, thanks to its diversified economy and strategic position in the Mediterranean. Japan saw its GDP increase by \$5,901.82 billion (1695.4%), supported by an advanced technology and automotive industry. South Korea showed extraordinary growth of 14408.6%, with an increase of \$2,789.50 billion, thanks to rapid

industrialization and technological innovation. Luxembourg, with a growth of 5027.4%, saw its GDP increase by \$93.51 billion, supported by the financial and banking sector. Mexico recorded a GDP increase of \$3,183.27 billion (3229.5%), benefiting from a young population and a competitive manufacturing industry. The Netherlands saw a GDP increase of \$1,332.83 billion (2316.0%), thanks to a strong logistics sector and an export-oriented economy. New Zealand recorded a GDP increase of \$267.40 billion (2419.9%), thanks to advanced agriculture and a growing tourism sector. Norway, with a GDP increase of \$687.79 billion (5278.5%), benefited from its oil resources and prudent economic management. Portugal saw its GDP increase by \$489.56 billion (2678.1%), thanks to an expanding tourism sector and structural economic reforms. Spain recorded a GDP increase of \$2,449.28 billion (2580.4%), supported by a strong tourism sector and increasing industrialization. Sweden saw a GDP increase of \$693.61 billion (1759.1%), benefiting from strong technological innovation and an advanced welfare system. Switzerland recorded a GDP increase of \$785.69 billion (1703.6%), thanks to a robust financial sector and an advanced pharmaceutical industry. Türkiye showed GDP growth of \$3,568.97 billion (5701.2%), supported by a growing population and rapid industrialization. The United Kingdom saw a GDP increase of \$3,789.11 billion (1877.0%), benefiting from a strong services industry and an open economy. The United States, with a GDP increase of \$26,274.70 billion (2448.0%), remains the world's leading economy, supported by a vast internal market and continuous technological innovation. In summary, the data analysis shows how OECD countries have experienced significant economic growth over the past fifty years. Common factors contributing to this growth include technological innovation, global economic integration, political stability, and favorable economic policies for investment. However, differences in growth rates reflect the varying economic strategies, available natural resources, and internal policies adopted by each country. For example, Ireland and South Korea recorded the highest percentage growths due to aggressive economic policies and attraction of foreign investments, while countries like Germany and the United States showed impressive absolute growths, benefiting from already solid and advanced economies. The diversity of strategies and available resources has created a varied economic landscape within the OECD, with each country finding its own path to growth and economic prosperity.

Economic Policies to Increase GDP in OECD Countries. The economic policies adopted by OECD countries to promote GDP growth are varied and reflect the specific economic conditions, natural resources, and national priorities of each country. A common denominator among OECD nations is investment in innovation and technology. Countries like South Korea and Japan have invested massively in research and development (R&D), becoming global leaders in advanced technology sectors such as electronics, robotics, and automotive. These investments have been supported by tax incentives for companies investing in R&D and the creation of technology parks to facilitate collaboration between industry and universities. In parallel, investment in infrastructure has been a pillar for many economies, such as the United States, where the recent "Infrastructure Investment and Jobs Act" aims to modernize existing infrastructure and create new jobs, further stimulating the economy. Expansive fiscal and monetary policies have been another crucial tool. In the European Union, many countries, like Germany and France, have adopted expansive fiscal policies, increasing public spending to stimulate aggregate demand. The European Central Bank has maintained low interest rates and implemented asset purchase programs to support liquidity in the financial system. Structural reforms have been fundamental in countries like Italy and Greece, where they have been implemented to improve labor market efficiency and business competitiveness. These reforms include labor market liberalization, reducing bureaucracy, and promoting entrepreneurship. In

parallel, open trade policies have allowed countries like the Netherlands and Belgium to become global logistics hubs. Their strategic position and advanced port infrastructures have facilitated international trade, reducing tariff and non-tariff barriers. Investment in education and continuous training has been another key factor for economic growth. Finland, with its educational system considered one of the best in the world, has focused on continuous training and digital skills, creating a highly qualified and adaptable workforce to the needs of the global market. Sustainability and renewable energy have been priorities for countries like Denmark and Norway, which have invested in renewable energies such as wind and hydroelectric. These investments have reduced dependence on fossil fuels and created new job opportunities in the clean energy sector. Attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) has played a crucial role for countries like Ireland. Thanks to very favorable tax policies, including a very low corporate tax rate, Ireland has become a hub for multinationals, leading to significant GDP growth and the creation of numerous jobs in the technology and pharmaceutical sectors. Labor market reforms have also had a significant impact on GDP growth. Spain, for example, has implemented reforms to make the labor market more flexible, facilitating hiring and reducing unemployment. The reforms include more flexible labor contracts and incentives for hiring young people and women. The United States has maintained a mix of expansive fiscal policies, technological innovation, and a robust labor market, leading to global leadership in sectors such as information technology and biotechnology. Germany has combined a strong industrial base with dual vocational training policies, integrating academic learning with work experience, creating a highly qualified workforce and supporting the competitiveness of its manufacturing industries. Ireland, with its success in attracting foreign direct investments, has transformed the country into a European technology hub. Favorable tax policies and integration into the European Union have attracted companies like Google, Apple, and Pfizer, significantly contributing to economic growth. South Korea, after the Asian financial crisis of the 1990s, implemented radical economic reforms, investing in R&D and improving the competitiveness of its industries. This led to explosive GDP growth, making South Korea one of the world's most dynamic economies. Norway, with prudent management of its oil resources through the government's sovereign fund, has been able to invest in infrastructure, education, and healthcare, ensuring economic stability for future generations. The diversity of strategies and available resources has created a varied economic landscape within the OECD, with each country finding its own path to economic growth and prosperity. These economic policies have enabled OECD countries to address global economic challenges and sustain robust and sustainable long-term economic growth. The analysis of the economic policies adopted by OECD countries reveals the importance of a multidimensional approach to promote GDP growth. Investments in innovation, infrastructure, education, and sustainability, combined with appropriate fiscal and monetary policies, have proven effective in supporting economic growth. The successful experiences of countries like the United States, Germany, Ireland, South Korea, and Norway offer important lessons on how well-designed and implemented economic policies can lead to positive and lasting economic outcomes.

Conclusions. The average GDP value of the considered OECD countries grew from \$118.59 billion in 1970 to \$2,911.2 billion in 2023, with a growth of +2354.9%. If we consider the percentage change values, we can see that GDP growth was highest in South Korea with 14,408.6%, in Ireland with +9110.2%, and in Türkiye with +5701.2% between 1970 and 2023. On average, between 1970 and 2023, GDP in the considered OECD countries grew by 3352%. However, some countries had GDP growth rates below the average. At the bottom of the ranking are Japan with +1652.8%, Italy with +1652.8%, and Greece with +1435.9%. This means that Italy's GDP grew about 16 times between 1970 and 2023. However, if Italy's GDP growth rate had been in line with the OECD average, its GDP would have grown 33.5 times. If we sum the GDP of the analyzed countries, we can calculate

the concentration index in 2023. The United States produces 36.13% of the total GDP of OECD countries. Japan is second with 8.26%, and Germany is third with 7.66%. Some countries have seen their GDP concentration among OECD countries grow between 1970 and 2023. For example, South Korea produced 0.63% of OECD countries' GDP in 1970; this value grew to 3.71%, a 491% increase in 2023. Similar results were obtained by Ireland with +275.17%, Türkiye with +136.31%, Norway with +119.09%, and Luxembourg with +108.86%. However, some countries have seen their share of total OECD GDP decrease between 1970 and 2023. Among these are Japan with -26.86%, Italy with -28.60%, and Greece with -37.43%. The data suggest that within the OECD there has been a redistribution of GDP from European countries, which grew less than the average, to non-European countries like South Korea, Australia, Canada, and Türkiye, which grew more than the average, with the exception of Japan. It is likely that international trade frictions between China and the USA and the Russia-Ukraine war could rebalance the GDP structure towards Europe within the OECD dynamics.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Variazione Assoluta del PIL nei paesi OCSE (1970-2023)

Politiche economiche per incrementare il PIL nei paesi OCSE